

Transparency in Local Governments: A Bibliometric Analysis

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Abstract

This study presents the importance of transparency in local governments and a bibliometric analysis of academic studies in this field. Transparency is a fundamental principle that increases the accountability of local governments, provides citizens with access to information and strengthens participatory democracy. In the study, academic studies in the Web of Science database examining the issue of transparency in local governments were analyzed. As a result of the analysis, it was determined that the first works were published in 1997 and reached the highest level in 2020, but there was a decrease in the number of publications after 2020. It has been observed that articles are dominant in the literature and fields such as political science, management and economics stand out. Studies focusing on SSCI and ESCI indexes have been frequently published by the Universities of Minho, Granada and London. The works are generally published in English and Spanish and have been published by major publishing houses such as Taylor & Francis, Elsevier and Sage. Contributions were made from more than 90 countries, especially Spain, America and England. Additionally, it has been determined that research focuses on sustainable development goals such as quality education and reducing inequalities.

Key words: Local Governments, Transparency, Bibliometric Analysis, Accounting, Governance

JEL Code: H70, H83, M40, O38

1. Introduction

“Local Government” and “Transparency” from a Conceptual Perspective

One of the organizations created by people, who are social creatures, to live together is local governments (Uçar et al., 2021: 117). Local governments are the

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units that are closest to the citizens and produce local goods and services (Es and Menteşe, 2018: 529; Çiftçioğlu and Aydın, 2109: 118). The activities and structure of local government units are determined by the country's sociocultural structure, economic tools and opportunities, and political cultures of the countries (Toprak, 2014: 21). After the rapid increase in urbanization, there has been a rapid increase in urban problems over time. If the solution to these problems and the required services are provided by the central government, it will cause both a great loss of time and delay in services, thus causing great losses (Yüksel, 1998: 91).

Central government-local government relations are among the important factors that determine the characteristics of public administration. Central and local government are subsystems of public administration. Therefore, the interaction between central and local governments constitutes one of the main concepts of management science and administrative law and is the axis of intergovernmental relations (Parlak, 2014: 8). The degree of centralization of countries or the extent to which they will be decentralized, that is, the extent to which the state will leave the legislative, executive and judicial powers to subunits, varies depending on historical and social differences that vary from country to country (Tekeli, 2021: 373).

The responsibilities of local governments are increasing day by day. Therefore, regardless of whether they are unitary or federal states, local governments must be defined constitutionally (Yılmaz, 2021: 85).

With globalization, there has been a serious change and transformation in the understanding of public administration, especially after 1980. The state has now evolved towards directing and controlling, rather than doing business. During this change process, there have been significant changes in the relationship network between the central government and local governments in favor of local governments (Akman, 2019: 2501). In the 1980s, the traditional public administration approach was replaced by a public administration approach that adopted a decentralized, soft hierarchy, flexible and minimal state approach (İzci and Geylani, 2021: 717).

A new process began with the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment held in Stockholm in 1972. Until then, civil society and local governments were not included in UN meetings, but now civil society and local governments have begun to be seen as partners, especially on issues related to the environment and humanitarian settlement (Bozlağan, 2004: 229).

Determining the decentralized method in the delivery of public services allows local governments to provide public services with broader powers. In such a method, local government units assume broad powers and responsibilities (Akıncı and Usta, 2021: 1).

Transparency is accepted as the basic feature of governance (Karaca and Yıldız Özsalmanlı, 2022: 121). The principles on which the concept of governance

is based have been explained by the Council of Europe. One of these principles is transparency (Council of Europe, 2007: 19-20). According to the report prepared by the World Bank (1989), good governance means “transparent, accountable and responsible management; It is defined as “an order in which active participation in the public decision-making process, a strong civil society and the rule of law prevail.” According to the reports prepared by the World Bank (1994) and OECD (1995), good governance is a "multi-faceted management" that should be built on the principles of "participation, transparency, accountability, efficiency, openness, auditing, ethics, virtue and merit in management". It has been stated that (Akinci et al., 2023: 2397).

In the study called "European Governance: A White Paper", accepted by the European Union Commission in 2001, he tried to reveal his own understanding of governance and defined the principles of governance as "openness", "participation", "accountability", “effectiveness” and “adaptation” are listed. Each of these principles is considered important by the Commission in terms of establishing a more democratic governance in the European Union (Commission of the European Communities, 2001: 10-11; European Union, 2024, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/>).

The diversity of manifestations of public administration is so great that there is no single definition. The principles and rules that apply to public administrations are, in principle, also valid for local governments. In local governments, there is a mayor and council with democratic legitimacy (Flidner, 2017: 3).

Transparency in Local Governments

Today, the sustainability of democratic societies depends on the effective implementation of governance principles. Among these principles, transparency has a critical role in ensuring the accountability of public institutions, establishing social trust and strengthening citizen participation. Local governments, as the public administration units closest to the public compared to the central administration, are of particular importance in terms of the applicability of the transparency principle.

The ability to make rapid administrative and political decisions and implement public policies in major crisis and disaster situations (such as Covid 19) has made it necessary to evolve into a structure that is accountable, transparent and capable of strategic economic interventions (Bimay and Kaypak, 2022: 437). This has been effective in bringing local governments to the forefront.

Adherence to the principle of transparency in local government decision-making processes, budget planning, resource allocation and provision of public services directly affects citizens' trust in the administration. In this context, transparency should be considered not only as an administrative principle but also as a prerequisite for democratic participation and control.

The idea that citizens can increase their own welfare more effectively by participating in decision-making processes in local governments is supported by the studies carried out in developing countries within the framework of models called "people managed development" or "participatory development" by the World Bank. It is implemented in projects (Şehitoğlu and Çarkçı, 2022: 249).

In democracies, the bodies of local governments are periodically determined by the votes of the people. Governments change hands through elections. The services and projects provided may be changed when they do not receive the necessary support from the public. Realizing democracy in the form of voting from election to election is no longer considered sufficient. In some cases, it may be possible to hold new elections between elections because the people are not satisfied with the services provided. Renewal of elections upon public demand is called "Recall Mechanism". This method is applied by 34 countries in the world (Aslan, 2023: 69).

The understanding of participatory democracy has been effective in making local governments more effective. The understanding of participatory democracy argues that in order to talk about real participation, citizens can actively participate in every stage of the political process (Dursun, 2004: 191-192; Eriş and Akıncı, 2019: 41). In the academic literature, numerous studies have been conducted on measuring, evaluating and improving transparency in local governments. However, these studies are generally limited to certain geographical regions or thematic areas and lack a global or systematic approach to the subject. This makes it difficult to conduct comparative analysis of transparency practices and disseminate examples of good governance. Non-governmental organizations that individuals establish and join with their free will are among the arguments of participatory democracy (Sartori, 1996: 125).

In order to ensure public participation in local government, there must be a transparent management approach (Gürün and Gezici, 2018: 67). In order to ensure the autonomy, transparency and effectiveness of local governments, the public must also participate in the planning and governance phase of cities (Dalgıç, 2023: 80).

Ensuring transparency in local governments is an important issue in terms of implementing the democratic local government approach. Citizens' knowledge of what the local government does will enable them to participate in decision-making processes individually and organizationally. This situation strengthens democracy in management. Transparency facilitates control over local government and thus the accountability process is strengthened (Bilge and Küçükaycan, 2013: 57).

In recent years, the development of information technologies and the spread of e-government applications have facilitated local governments to become more open and accessible. However, institutional will, legal regulations and social demands are among the main factors determining the level of transparency, as well

as technological infrastructure. Therefore, transparency should be considered as a matter of administrative culture rather than a technical application.

Communication and information technologies have had a great impact on transparency and transparency. Transparency in the traditional sense is used to mean that public institutions and organizations carry out their work openly, disclose their decisions to the public and be open to public inspection. Nowadays, the concept of digital transparency comes to the fore. Digital transparency operates with the same logic as the concept of transparency used in the traditional sense. However, collecting, processing and sharing data through information and communication technologies is specific to digital transparency. Digital transparency makes it possible for public institutions and organizations and companies to display data more transparently, to make decisions with the data obtained, and for users or the public to be informed about and audit the data (Keskin and Keloğlu İşler, 2023: 111-112). Digital transparency has also changed the way power is achieved because it is information-oriented. Power in digital transparency comes from eliminating uncertainty with multiple stakeholders (Özmen et al., 2020: 58).

Financial transparency is one of the primary areas where transparency must be ensured. Financial transparency is important in order to implement effective fiscal policies and manage financial risks (Turan, 2014: 9).

Transparency has affected crisis management in different geographies of the world and has been considered a correct method of struggle. This situation was also confirmed in the COVID'19 epidemic (Gedikkaya, 2022: 753). As a matter of fact, the World Health Organization has established good risk management communication on five principles, including transparency. Transparency is also very important to create a climate of trust. Transparency can also be considered as a precaution against the possibility of misinformation and rumors spreading rapidly (Şenol and Avcı, 2020: 342). Transparency is also effective in building trust. When there is no transparency, the possibility of misinformation and rumors spreading increases. As a result, increasing transparency in local governments should be considered as a strategic necessity not only in terms of the effectiveness of public services but also in terms of protecting and developing democratic values. In this context, a comprehensive examination of transparency practices at the local level, both theoretically and empirically, will make significant contributions to the discipline of public administration.

This study aims to understand the development and trends of the scientific literature on how the concept of transparency is handled in local governments. The scope of the research consists of 784 pieces of scientific literature in the "Web of Science" databases (<https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/basic-search>). Data regarding 784 scientific publications obtained through the query made in the database were analyzed with the bibliometric analysis method in terms of various

variables. In this study, Web of Science (WoS) (<https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/basic-search>), the world's most widely used database, was preferred. In the study, no restrictions other than "topic" and "keywords" were applied during the query phase. The query performed on 28.06.2024 to create the data set is as follows:

"Transparency " (Topic) AND "Local Government" (Topic)

The access link for the query is as follows:

<https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/summary/77eec3fa-4a88-4ef4-a531-d2a5954b52ea-f7b0b2c5/relevance/1>

After the data cleaning phase, the data of 784 publications analyzed with Excel and Vosviewer programs were analyzed with tables, graphs and maps, and the findings were presented to the attention of the readers.

2. Literature Review

The issue of transparency in local governments is comprehensively addressed by many scientific studies that vary in size and are conducted in various countries and regions. For example; Hausteijn and Lorson (2023) focused on the transparency of local government financial statements and citizens' perception of these statements. Stanic (2023) investigated the effects of gender imbalance on local government budget transparency.

Nguyen Trong Binh and Nguyen Quang Giai (2022) discussed the level of transparency and its social impacts in local governments in Vietnam. Stanus (2022) discussed local government transparency processes in new democracies. Rodriguez Martin et al (2022) examined the main factors of transparency in urban waste management. Stanus (2022) described the compliance of local governments in Romania with transparency regulations.

Rieznik and Lee (2021) investigated the effects of corruption perception and transparency on public trust in local governments.

Tavares and da Cruz (2020) explained the transparency of local government websites within the framework of the political market. Sofyani, Riyadh and Fahlevi (2020) emphasized the role of information technology governance on local government service quality, accountability and transparency. Hu et al (2020) presented a model to evaluate the public's satisfaction with local government budget transparency in China.

Kim and Lee (2019) explored citizen participation, processes, and local government transparency. Garrido-Rodriguez et al (2019) examined the factors affecting the transparency model in Spanish local governments.

Roge and Lennon (2018) discussed internal transparency, efficiency and effectiveness criteria in measuring local government performance.

Garrido-Rodriguez et al (2017) evaluated the impact of political sign on Spanish local government transparency in multidimensional analysis. Gabriel (2017) examined the transparency and accountability levels of Bongabon municipal council members.

da Cruz et al. (2016) detailed the measurement of local government transparency. Ferraz Esteves de Araujo and Tejedro-Romero (2016) examined the determinants ranking the transparency levels of local governments. Oztoprak and Ruijer (2016) analyzed different variations of the local government transparency code in England.

Ferry et al. (2015) discussed the relationship between accountability and transparency in the UK.

Cuadrado-Ballesteros (2014) investigated the effects of functional centralization and externalization on local government transparency.

Albalate del Sol (2013) examined the institutional, economic and social determinants of local government transparency. MacManus et al (2013) discussed the balance between transparency and privacy rights in cybersecurity at the local government level. Pontones Rosa and Perez Morote (2013) discussed the control function of social services in Spanish local governments and its impact on transparency.

Esteller-More and Polo Otero (2012) examined the processes of responding to financial transparency of local governments.

Guillamon et al. (2011) investigated the factors that determine the financial transparency of local governments. French (2011) discussed the potential for local governments to increase the legitimacy of transparency and public participation in pandemic flu planning.

Grimmelikhuijsen (2010) examined the contributions of transparency of public decision-making processes to building trust in local governments.

Piotrowski and Van Ryzin (2007) examined citizens' attitudes towards local government transparency.

Dowley (2006) discussed local government transparency in Central Eastern Europe.

3. Methodology

Purpose and Problems of the Research

The concept of transparency in local governments stands out as one of the fundamental elements of democratic governance and the scientific interest in this field is increasing; however, a comprehensive and systematic analysis of the

literature in various dimensions such as the development course over time, research trends on the subject, interdisciplinary distribution, citation profiles, researcher contributions, institutional and geographical spread and keyword usage patterns has not yet been sufficiently carried out. In this context, the main problem of the study is to present a holistic picture of the current situation in literature by revealing the quantitative and tendencies of academic studies on transparency in local governments within the framework of a multidimensional analysis.

This study aims to understand the development and trends of the scientific literature on how the concept of transparency is handled in local governments. The basic research problems to which answers are sought within this framework are;

- What is the quantitative development of the scientific literature on transparency in local governments over the years? What is the trend?
- What is the quantitative distribution of the scientific literature on transparency in local governments according to document type?
- What is the quantitative distribution of the scientific literature on transparency in local governments according to Citation Topics Meso?
- What is the quantitative distribution of the scientific literature on transparency in local governments according to Researcher Profiles?
- What is the quantitative distribution of scientific literature on transparency in local governments according to Web of Science Categories?
- What is the quantitative distribution of scientific literature on transparency in local governments according to the Web of Science Index?
- What is the quantitative distribution of scientific literature on transparency in local governments according to Affiliations?
- What is the quantitative distribution of scientific literature on transparency in local governments according to Publication Titles?
- What is the quantitative distribution of scientific literature on transparency in local governments according to Languages?
- What is the quantitative distribution of the scientific literature on transparency in local governments according to Countries/Regions?
- What is the quantitative distribution of scientific literature on transparency in local governments according to Publishers?
- What is the quantitative distribution of scientific literature on transparency in local governments according to Research Areas?
- What is the quantitative distribution of scientific literature on transparency in local governments according to Funding Agencies?

- What is the quantitative distribution of the scientific literature on transparency in local governments according to Sustainable Development Goals?
- What is the quantitative distribution and mapping of the scientific literature on transparency in local governments according to the keywords used?

Scope of Research

There are numerous academic studies on the relationship between local governments and transparency. The Web of Science database provides healthy bibliometric data in terms of the academic quality and systematic accessibility of international studies in this field. In addition, the Web of Science database contains sufficient quantity and quality academic studies to examine the relationship between local governments and transparency. In this context, the Web of Science database was deemed appropriate for the analysis. The scope of the research consists of 784 pieces of scientific literature in the "Web of Science" databases (<https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/basic-search>). Data regarding 784 scientific publications obtained through the query made in the database were analyzed in terms of various variables.

Creation of Data Set and Method

Bibliometric analysis is a method that includes the numerical evaluation of publications produced in a specific field, period and region and the relationships between them (<https://cabim.ulakbim.gov.tr>, 23.11.2023). In other words, bibliometrics enables the analysis of scientific journals and other communication tools through mathematical and statistical techniques; In this way, it categorizes scientific publications and performs a systematic analysis. This method aims to evaluate, describe and monitor published research (Ellegaard and Wallin, 2015; Tutar et al., 2023). Bibliometric analysis aims to reveal the general structure of a particular discipline by statistically examining the collaborations between countries and authors, citations, institutions and publication years of selected publications (Özbağ, et al., 2019). It also identifies the volume and growth pattern of literature for an emerging field, evaluates academic contributions, and provides a retrospective look at the literature (Guleria and Kaur, 2021).

Bibliometric analysis results are generally presented through tables and mapping/visualization techniques (Beşel and Yardımcıoğlu, 2017; Donthu et al., 2021). Mapping/visualization-based programs that provide graphical support offer effective methods in solving clustering problems in bibliometric analyzes (Guney and Ala, 2024). In this study, Vosviewer (<https://www.vosviewer.com/>) program was used for mapping and visualization. Vosviewer visualizes researcher collaboration and trends in research topics by creating bibliometric maps (Eck and Waltman, 2017). Vosviewer is a platform used for clustering solutions and co-

occurrence analyzes based on citation relationships of scientific publications (Eck and Waltman, 2017; Ding and Yang, 2020).

Bibliometric analysis is a systematic review method based on certain criteria and requires publications to be of a certain standard and order (Güney and Ala, 2024). In this study, Web of Science (WoS) (<https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/basic-search>), which is the most widely used database worldwide, was preferred. In the research, no restrictions were imposed on the questioning phase other than "topic" and "keywords". The query performed on 28.06.2024 to create the data set is as follows:

"Transparency " (Topic) AND "Local Government" (Topic)

The access link for the query is as follows:

<https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/summary/77ecc3fa-4a88-4ef4-a531-d2a5954b52ea-f7b0b2c5/relevance/1>

After the data cleaning phase, the data of 784 publications analyzed with Excel and Vosviewer programs were analyzed with tables, graphs and maps, and the findings were presented to the attention of the readers.

4. Findings

Growth and Trend by Publication Year

Fig.1 shows the number of records for each year from 1997 to 2024 and the trend line added to this data set. In the period from 1997 to 2007, registration numbers are quite low and show a slow increase.

Fig. 1: Publication Year and Trend

Source: <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/analyze-results/>

A significant increase in the number of registrations has been observed since 2010. This increase accelerated in 2014 and continued until 2020, and 2020 reached the highest value with 80 registrations. Then, there was a slight decrease in 2021, and an increase was observed again in 2022. However, the decline in registration numbers continued in 2023 and 2024. The added trend line shows that overall there is an upward trend in enrollment numbers over the years. This trend shows that academic studies or research topics have received increasing attention over the years and the recorded data is increasing every year.

Distribution by Document Type

The pie chart below shows the distribution of various document types across a total of 784 records. The document type with the highest share is articles, with a rate of 81.888%, and is the most dominant document type with 642 records. This is followed by papers with a rate of 16.327% and 128 registrations. Early access documents rank third with a rate of 2.551% and 20 registrations. Book chapters attract attention with a rate of 2.296% and 18 records. Review articles are on the list with a rate of 1.913% and 15 records..

Fig.2: Publication Type

Source: <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/analyze-results/>

Editorial content has a very low share with 0.383% and 3 records. Finally, books are the least represented document type with 0.128% and only 1 record. This situation shows that the article genre still has a central position in the sharing of scientific knowledge and other document types remain supportive.

Distribution of Publications by Citation Topics Meso (Top 15)

The data in the table 1 shows the distribution of various academic citation topics by number of records. The subject with the highest number of registrations is political science, with 275 registrations, reflecting the intensity of studies in this field. The field of management ranks second with 163 records, while economics ranks third with 57 records. The subjects of human geography, Asian studies and climate change are represented at the medium level with 27, 18 and 16 entries respectively. Subjects such as law and sustainability science have less intensive studies, with 14 and 12 entries respectively.

Table 1: Citation Topics Meso

Citation Topics Meso	Record Count	% of 784
Political Science	275	35.077
Management	163	20.791
Economics	57	7.270
Human Geography	27	3.444
Asian Studies	18	2.296
Climate Change	16	2.041
Law	14	1.786
Sustainability Science	12	1.531
Forestry	11	1.403
Communication	11	1.403
Social Reform	10	1.276
Healthcare Policy	9	1.148
Design & Manufacturing	7	0.893
Hospitality, Leisure, Sport & Tourism	7	0.893
Nursing	6	0.765

Source: <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/analyze-results/>

Subjects such as forestry, communication and social reform are on the list with numbers varying between 10-11 entries. Fields such as health policy, design and production, accommodation and tourism are represented with lower registration numbers. Various other scientific topics are included in the table with numbers ranging from 1 to 5 records. The findings show that political science is by far the most intensively studied field in the distribution of academic citation topics, followed by social sciences such as management and economics, while other topics are more limitedly represented.

Researcher Profiles (Top 20)

The publications of the 20 researchers who contributed the most to the publications contributed by a total of 1654 authors are listed according to the number of records. Among the researchers with the highest number of registrations are names such as Laurence Ferry, Francisca Tejedo-Romero, Mihaela Bronic,

Joaquim Filipe Ferraz Esteves Araujo and Beatriz Cuadrado-Ballesteros, each of whom stands out with 10 registrations.

Table 2: Researcher Profiles

Researcher Profiles	Record Count	% of 784
Ferry, Laurence	10	1.276
Tejedo-Romero, Francisca	10	1.276
Bronic, Mihaela	10	1.276
Araujo, Joaquim Filipe Ferraz Esteves	10	1.276
Cuadrado-Ballesteros, Beatriz	8	1.020
Guillamon, Maria-Dolores	8	1.020
Benito, Bernardino	7	0.893
Worthy, Ben	7	0.893
Galera, Andrés Navarro	7	0.893
Mackic, Velibor	7	0.893
Stanić, Branko	6	0.765
Royo, Sonia	5	0.638
Saez-Martín, A.	5	0.638
Bastida, Francisco	5	0.638
Frías-Aceituno, José-Valeriano	5	0.638
Tavares, Antonio F.	5	0.638
Ríos-Martínez, Ana María	5	0.638
Torres, Lourdes	5	0.638
Ott, Katarina	5	0.638
Yetano, Ana	4	0.510

Source: <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/analyze-results/>

Other important researchers such as Maria-Dolores Guillamon and Bernardino Benito attract attention with 8 and 7 records. In addition, names such as Branko Stanić with 6 recordings, Sonia Royo, A. Saez-Martín and Francisco Bastida with 5 recordings also make important contributions. Among other researchers who have lower registration numbers but still find a place in the academic literature, there are many names with 3 and 2 registrations. This distribution shows that certain researchers stand out in terms of academic productivity and impact, while others contribute with a more limited number of publications. These data provide an important resource for assessing the intensity of academic research activities and the impact of certain researchers on the field.

Web of Science Categories (Top 25)

In the analysis made according to Web of Science categories, it is seen that the highest number of registrations is in the field of Public Administration (214). This field is followed by categories such as Political Science (105), Economics (90),

Business Finance (69) and Information Science Librarianship (69). Fields such as Management (58), Environmental Studies (54), Regional Urban Planning (53) and Business Administration (40) also have a notable number of publications. Environmental Sciences (39), Social Sciences Interdisciplinary (33) and Development Studies (31) categories also have significant publication numbers. More technical and specific fields such as Communications (30), Computer Science Information Systems (30) and Green Sustainable Science and Technology (27) are also on the list. Fields such as Law (25), Computer Science Interdisciplinary Applications (22) and Geography (18) have relatively fewer publications.

Table 3: Web of Science Categories

Web of Science Categories	Record Count	% of 784
Public Administration	214	27.296
Political Science	105	13.393
Economics	90	11.480
Business Finance	69	8.801
Information Science Library Science	69	8.801
Management	58	7.398
Environmental Studies	54	6.888
Regional Urban Planning	53	6.760
Business	40	5.102
Environmental Sciences	39	4.974
Social Sciences Interdisciplinary	33	4.209
Development Studies	31	3.954
Communication	30	3.827
Computer Science Information Systems	30	3.827
Green Sustainable Science Technology	27	3.444
Law	25	3.189
Computer Science Interdisciplinary Applications	22	2.806
Geography	18	2.296
Urban Studies	18	2.296
Area Studies	16	2.041
Computer Science Theory Methods	15	1.913
Public Environmental Occupational Health	12	1.531
Sociology	12	1.531
Social Issues	11	1.403
Engineering Environmental	10	1.276

Source: <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/analyze-results/>

Fields such as area studies (16), Computer Science Theory and Methods (15) and Public Environmental Occupational Health (12) also attract attention. Social sciences and engineering fields such as Sociology (12), Social Problems (11) and Environmental Engineering (10) are less represented in terms of the number of publications. Although not included in the table; Categories such as

Multidisciplinary Sciences (9), Artificial Intelligence (8) and Education Educational Research (8) have a more limited number of publications. Many other disciplines are represented by lower enrollment numbers, ranging from 1 to 7. This shows that the density of publications in various academic fields varies considerably, with some areas attracting more research attention than others.

Web of Science Index

This classification, made according to the Web of Science Index, measures the impact of academic literature in various fields. The Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI) has the highest number of records, followed by the Emerging Sources Citation Index (ESCI).

Table 4: Web of Science Index

Web of Science Index	Record Count	% of 784
Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI)	384	48.980
Emerging Sources Citation Index (ESCI)	234	29.847
Conference Proceedings Citation Index – Social Science & Humanities (CPCI-SSH)	87	11.097
Science Citation Index Expanded (SCI-EXPANDED)	79	10.077
Conference Proceedings Citation Index – Science (CPCI-S)	63	8.036
Book Citation Index – Social Sciences & Humanities (BKCI-SSH)	18	2.296
Arts & Humanities Citation Index (A&HCI)	4	0.510
Book Citation Index – Science (BKCI-S)	3	0.383

Source: <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/analyze-results/>

Social Sciences and Humanities Conference Proceedings Citation Index (CPCI-SSH) and Expanded Science Citation Index (SCI-EXPANDED) are among other important indexes and have an important role in measuring the citation and impact of academic studies.

Affiliations (Top 15)

The table 5 shows the distribution of 784 published academic articles by universities (Top 15). Universidade Do Minho has the highest number of publications, with 19 articles, accounting for 2,423% of the total publications. The University of Granada follows with 2,296% with 18 articles.

Table 5: Affiliations

Affiliations	Record Count	% of 784
Universidade Do Minho	19	2.423
University Of Granada	18	2.296

University Of London	17	2.168
University Of Murcia	17	2.168
Universidad De Castilla La Mancha	14	1.786
University Of Salamanca	12	1.531
Institute Of Public Finance	11	1.403
University Of Zaragoza	11	1.403
State University Of New York Suny System	10	1.276
Durham University	9	1.148
Ministry Of Education Science Of Ukraine	9	1.148
State University Of New York Suny Albany	9	1.148
State University System Of Florida	9	1.148
University Of Zagreb	9	1.148
Birkbeck University London	7	0.893

Source: <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/analyze-results/>

University of London and University of Murcia have a share of 2.168% with 17 articles. Universidad de Castilla La Mancha, 14 articles (1.786%), University of Salamanca 12 articles (1.531%), Institute of Public Finance and University of Zaragoza 11 articles each (1.403%), State University of New York Suny System 10 articles (1.276%) published. Additionally, Durham University, Ministry of Education Science of Ukraine, State University of New York Suny Albany, State University System of Florida and University of Zagreb published 9 articles each (1.148%), and Birkbeck University London published 7 articles (0.893%). This data includes information on international collaborations and joint publications of various universities and academic institutions. In particular, institutions such as the University of Minho in Portugal, the University of Granada in Spain and the University of London have extensive international collaboration networks. Institutions such as the University of Murcia, the University of Castilla La Mancha and the University of Salamanca also have extensive academic networks, while the Treasury Institute, which specialises in public finance, is also notable. Institutions such as the SUNY System and the Florida State University System from the USA also play a prominent role in international collaborations.

Publication Title (Top 25)

The table 6 shows the distribution of 784 academic articles published in the field according to the 25 most publishing journals. Local Government Studies has the highest number of publications, with 24 articles, accounting for 3,061% of the total publications. Government Information Quarterly ranks second with a share of 2.551% with 20 articles, while Sustainability magazine has a share of 2.041% with 16 articles. Public Money Management published 14 articles (1.786%), Lex Localis Journal of Local Self Government published 12 articles (1.531%), International Review of Administrative Sciences and Public Administration Review published 11 articles each (1.403%).

Table 6: Publication Titles

Publication Titles	Record Count	% of 784
Local Government Studies	24	3.061
Government Information Quarterly Sustainability	20	2.551
Public Money Management	16	2.041
Lex Localis Journal Of Local Self Government	14	1.786
International Review Of Administrative Sciences	12	1.531
Public Administration Review	11	1.403
Public Management Review	11	1.403
International Journal Of Public Sector Management	9	1.148
Financial Accountability Management	8	1.020
Journal Of Public Budgeting Accounting Financial Management	7	0.893
Medunarodni Znanstveni Simpozij Gospodarstvo Istocne Hrvatske Jucer Danas Sutra	7	0.893
Transforming Government People Process And Policy	6	0.765
Advances in Social Science Education And Humanities Research	6	0.765
Commonwealth Journal Of Local Governance	5	0.638
International Journal Of Public Administration	5	0.638
Journal Of Cleaner Production	5	0.638
Journal Of Public Affairs	5	0.638
Online Information Review	5	0.638
Procedia Social And Behavioral Sciences	5	0.638
Public Administration And Development	5	0.638
Public Administration And Information Technology	5	0.638
Revista De Contabilidad Spanish Accounting Review	5	0.638
Administration Society	4	0.510
American Review Of Public Administration	4	0.510

Source: <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/analyze-results/>

Public Management Review published 9 articles (1.148%), International Journal of Public Sector Management published 8 articles (1.020%), Financial Accountability Management and Journal of Public Budgeting Accounting Financial Management published 7 articles each (0.893%). Medunarodni Znanstveni Simpozij Gospodarstvo Istocne Hrvatske Jucer Danas Sutra and Transforming Government People Process and Policy 6 articles each (0.765%), Advances in Social Science Education and Humanities Research, Commonwealth Journal of Local Governance, International Journal of Public Administration, Journal of Cleaner Production , Journal of Public Affairs, Online Information Review, Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences, Public Administration and Development, Public Administration and Information Technology and Revista de Contabilidad Spanish Accounting Review 5 articles each (0.638%), Administration Society and

American Review of Public Administration published 4 articles each (0.510%). These data provide an important resource for researchers and academics focusing on topics such as public policy, public services management, environmental management and economic policy. There are also various publications in conference proceedings and platforms that promote international collaborations, which shows how academic interaction and knowledge sharing are developing on a global scale.

Language

The table 7 shows the variety of languages commonly used in academic literature on the subject. English is by far the most used language, accounting for the vast majority (92.857%) of total publications.

Table 7: Publicat Languages

Languages	Record Count	% of 784
English	728	92.857
Spanish	35	4.464
Portuguese	7	0.893
Russian	4	0.510
Croatian	2	0.255
Catalan	1	0.128
Chinese	1	0.128
Czech	1	0.128
German	1	0.128
Hungarian	1	0.128
Malay	1	0.128
Polish	1	0.128
Slovak	1	0.128

Source: <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/analyze-results/>

Spanish and Portuguese are widely used in academic studies, especially from Latin America and the Iberian Peninsula. While Russian can be associated with research in Slavic languages, it can be said that there are also publications in other languages such as Croatian, Czech, German, Hungarian, Polish and Slovak. demic literature on the subject. English is by far the most used language, accounting for the vast majority (92.857%) of total publications. These data show that researchers publishing globally conduct studies in different language and cultural contexts and that these studies are important in terms of international cooperation and exchange of information.

Countries/Regions (Top 20)

The table 8 shows that different countries and regions have contributed to research in the academic literature on the subject. Spain (15,561%) and the USA (14,668%) stand out as the countries with the most publications, reflecting the strong presence and contributions of these countries in academic research.

Table 8: Countries/Regions

Countries/Regions	Record Count	% of 784
Spain	122	15.561
Usa	115	14.668
England	74	9.439
Peoples R China	72	9.184
Indonesia	56	7.143
Australia	46	5.867
Italy	33	4.209
Portugal	27	3.444
Canada	25	3.189
South Africa	20	2.551
South Korea	18	2.296
Croatia	17	2.168
Netherlands	16	2.041
Sweden	14	1.786
Brazil	13	1.658
Czech Republic	12	1.531
Germany	12	1.531
Russia	11	1.403
Bangladesh	10	1.276
Ukraine	10	1.276

Source: <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/analyze-results/>

The United Kingdom, the People's Republic of China, Indonesia and Australia are among other important countries with a significant number of publications. It is seen that European countries such as Portugal, Croatia, Italy, Canada and South Africa also contribute to the international literature by actively conducting research. These data highlight the importance of diverse geographic regions and cultural contexts within the global research network, thus promoting the integration of different perspectives and fields of scientific study.

Publishers (Top 10)

The table 9 shows the contributions of the top 10 publishers who work in various fields of academic literature on the subject and have the most publications. Major publishing houses such as Taylor & Francis, Elsevier, Emerald Group Publishing, Wiley, Sage and Springer Nature host the most publications.

Table 9: Publishers

Publishers	Record Count	% of 784
Taylor & Francis	137	17.474

Elsevier	78	9.949
Emerald Group Publishing	67	8.546
Wiley	65	8.291
Sage	50	6.378
Springer Nature	49	6.250
Mdpi	21	2.679
IEEE	15	1.913
Acad Conferences Ltd	11	1.403
Inst Local Self-Government		
Maribor	11	1.403

Source: <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/analyze-results/>

In addition, publishing houses focused on technical issues such as IEEE and open access publishers such as Mdpi also stand out as important publication sources. These data show how the academic world produces knowledge on a diversified and global scale through various publishers.

Research Areas (Top 20)

The table 10 shows the wide interdisciplinary diversity on the subject. The largest enrollments are in areas focused on social sciences, such as public administration and business economics.

Table 10: Research Areas

Research Areas	Record Count	% of 784
Public Administration	242	30.867
Business Economics	210	26.786
Government Law	128	16.327
Environmental Sciences Ecology	76	9.694
Information Science Library Science	69	8.801
Computer Science	56	7.143
Social Sciences Other Topics	39	4.974
Science Technology Other Topics	36	4.592
Development Studies	31	3.954
Communication	30	3.827
Engineering	28	3.571
Geography	18	2.296
Urban Studies	18	2.296
Area Studies	16	2.041
Public Environmental Occupational Health	12	1.531
Sociology	12	1.531
Social Issues	11	1.403
Education Educational Research	9	1.148
Water Resources	8	1.020
Energy Fuels	6	0.765

Source: <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/analyze-results/>

Subjects such as public administration, state law, environmental sciences and ecology have an important share. Information sciences, librarianship, computer science and technology-related topics are also common research topics. Fields such as development studies, communications, engineering and geography were also notably represented. These data show that academic research has a structure that spreads over a wide spectrum and deepens at the intersections of different disciplines. The diversity in research areas shows that scientific knowledge is enriched by being addressed from various perspectives and contributes to the production of knowledge on a global scale.

Funding Agencies (Top 15)

The table 11 shows the support provided to scientific studies on the subject by various research funding organizations around the world. Institutions such as the Government of Spain, the National Natural Science Foundation of China (NSFC), the European Union (EU), and the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) are among the leading support providers.

Table 11: Funding Agencies

Funding Agencies	Record Count	% of 784
Spanish Government	18	2.296
National Natural Science Foundation Of China Nsf	11	1.403
European Union Eu	10	1.276
Fundacao Para A Ciencia E A Tecnologia Fct	9	1.148
Croatian Science Foundation	7	0.893
Croatian Science Foundation Csf	7	0.893
Uk Research Innovation Ukri	7	0.893
Economic Social Research Council Esrc	5	0.638
National Office Of Philosophy And Social Sciences	4	0.510
National Science Foundation Nsf	4	0.510
National Social Science Fund Of China	4	0.510
Ministry Of Research And Technology Of The Republic Of Indonesia Ristek	3	0.383
Norte Portugal Regional Operational Programme Norte 2020 Under The Portugal 2020 Partnership Agreement Through The European Regional Development Fund Efd	3	0.383
Social Sciences And Humanities Research Council Of Canada Sshrc	3	0.383
Academic Sinica	2	0.255

Source: <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/analyze-results/>

Additionally, other institutions such as the Croatian Science Foundation (CSF), the UK Research and Innovation Institute (UKRI), and the China National

Fund for Social Sciences also offer significant support. These funds cover a wide range of research areas, from social sciences to engineering, environmental sciences to health sciences. Support from national and local governments to international organizations reflects the diversity of academic research and its contribution to the advancement of scientific knowledge on a global scale.

Sustainable Development Goals

The table 12 shows the areas of focus of academic research on sustainable development goals. Quality education, reducing inequalities and eliminating poverty stand out among the most studied topics.

Table 12: Sustainable Development Goals

Sustainable Development Goals	Record Count	% of 784
Quality Education	116	14.796
Reduced Inequality	66	8.418
No Poverty	57	7.270
Sustainable Cities And Communities	44	5.612
Good Health And Well Being	33	4.209
Industry Innovation And Infrastructure	31	3.954
Climate Action	28	3.571
Decent Work And Economic Growth	20	2.551
Peace And Justice Strong Institutions	18	2.296
Life On Land	17	2.168
Clean Water And Sanitation	13	1.658
Responsible Consumption And Production	5	0.638
Affordable And Clean Energy	4	0.510
Life Below Water	3	0.383
Zero Hunger	2	0.255
Gender Equality	1	0.128

Not: 421 record(s) (53.699%) do not contain data in the field being analyzed.

Source: <https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/analyze-results/>

Additionally, other important areas such as sustainable cities and communities, health and wellness, industry, innovation and infrastructure are also attracting attention. Research conducted towards these goals contributes to promoting sustainable development at the global level and achieving these goals. However, some areas appear to have received less research, such as responsible consumption and production, clean water and sanitation. There is no definition of sustainable development goals in 421 of 784 scientific publications (53.699%). These data show the areas where academic research on sustainable development goals is focused. The most studied topics are quality education (SDG 4), reducing inequalities (SDG 10) and eradicating poverty (SDG 1). In addition, other important areas such as sustainable cities and communities (SDG 11), health and well-being (SDG 3), industry, innovation and infrastructure (SDG 9) are also noteworthy. Research on these goals contributes to the promotion and achievement of

sustainable development at the global level. However, it is seen that there are some areas (for example, responsible consumption and production - SDG 12, clean water and sanitation - SDG 6) where less research has been done, indicating that these topics require more attention.

Keyword Analysis

The keyword with the highest usage frequency is "local government", which was used 236 times and reached a total link strength of 396. This shows how important the topic of local government is in research and how strongly it is related to other topics. This is followed by "transparency", which was used 146 times and has a total link strength of 275. The issue of transparency is of critical importance for public administration and governance studies, and this is clearly seen in the tabular data. "Accountability" has been used 53 times and ranks third with a connection strength of 109, which shows that accountability has an important place in academic research.

Other important keywords include "e-government" (41 uses, 81 link strength), "local governments" (35 uses, 52 link strength) and "social media" (27 uses, 61 link strength). E-government and social media play an important role in modern management approaches and interaction with citizens. "Municipalities" (25 uses, 59 tie strength) and "governance" (24 uses, 35 tie strength) also have high usage and tie strength values, showing how widely municipalities and general governance issues have been studied.

Keywords with lower frequency of use but still significant link strength include "corruption" (22 uses, 33 link strength), "decentralization" (19 uses, 32 link strength) and "open government" (19 uses, 52 link strength) is located. Corruption, centralism and open government are among the frequently discussed topics in public administration and policy studies.

Concepts such as "Citizen participation" (18 uses, 38 link strengths), "participation" (18 uses, 42 link strengths) and "sustainability" (18 uses, 34 link strengths) represent other important themes that the studies focus on. Other important keywords for the public sector include "public sector" (16 uses, 27 link strength), "budget transparency" (15 uses, 24 link strength) and "good governance" (15 uses, 30 link strength). These concepts emphasize the importance of public administration and financial transparency issues in academic literature.

Keywords like "public administration" (14 uses, 29 link strength) and "spain" (14 uses, 46 link strength) also have remarkable link strength. Studies on

Spain in particular stand out in connection with issues such as local government and transparency.

Other noteworthy concepts include "trust" (14 uses, 25 link strength), "democracy" (11 uses, 28 link strength) and "corporate social responsibility" (9 uses, 12 link strength). These concepts show the place of values such as trust, democracy and corporate social responsibility in public administration and policy studies.

Less frequently used but important keywords also attract attention. For example, concepts such as "sustainable development", "open data" and "participatory budgeting" show that sustainability and the use of open data are becoming increasingly important in local governments. Additionally, keywords such as "audit", "leadership" and "civil society" point to the role of leadership and civil society in the process of ensuring transparency. These findings show that research on transparency in local governments is addressed in a wide range and from different perspectives. As a suggestion for future research, in addition to existing keywords, it can be suggested to examine concepts such as "smart cities", "social accountability" and "public information" more deeply. Additionally, further comparative research on studies conducted in different countries and regions can contribute to the understanding of transparency practices in local governments on a global scale. In this way, it will be possible to fill the gaps in the literature and increase knowledge on transparency in local governments.

Fig.3: Network, Overlay ve Density Visulation, (Occurrences) for Keywords
Source: Vosviewer.

As a result of mapping the keywords via Vosviewer, 75 keywords were grouped in 9 different clusters. It is possible to specify these groups and their elements as follows:

Cluster 1 (14 items): citizen participation civil society decentralisation decentralization democracy ghana good governance governance indonesia participatory budgeting social accountability tanzania trust vietnam

Cluster 2 (11 items): access to information accountability audit austerity budgeting efficiency england financial sustainability local governance public sector sustainable developmer

Cluster 3 (11 items): corporate social respons disclosure e-governance e-government information disclosure legitimacy nigeria performance spain sustainability websites

Cluster 4 (10 items): china fiscal transparency government transparen local governments participation public administration public management public participation public policy transparency

Cluster 5 (10 items): corruption evaluation ict local government municipality new public managemer open data open government open government data smart cities

Cluster 6 (9 items): citizens e-democracy e-participation engagement facebook government social media twitter web 2.0

Cluster 7 (5 items): bangladesh communication internet municipalities public information

Cluster 8 (4 items): budget transparency croatia gender political economy

Cluster 9 (1 item): leadership

Citation Analysis (Top 20)

The table 13 shows the citation numbers and link strengths of the 20 most cited publications. The most cited study is Piotrowski (2007) with 351 citations and 64 links, while Kim (2009) is in second place with 209 citations and 4 links. Grimmelikhuijsen (2012) ranks third with 199 citations and 27 connections. In general, high citation numbers indicate that these studies have a significant impact in the academic literature, while link numbers can also be considered as an indicator of the studies' relationship with other studies.

Table 13: Citation Analysis

Rank	Document	Citations	Links
1	Piotrowski (2007)	351	64
2	Kim (2009)	209	4
3	Grimmelikhuijsen (2012)	199	27
4	Preuss (2009)	190	0
5	Kim (2012)	186	15
6	Kim (2010)	180	6
7	Al-Hujran (2015)	179	0
8	Guillamon (2011)	171	1
9	Brender (2003)	170	5
10	Haro-De-Rosario (2018)	160	11
11	Garcia-Sanchez (2013)	152	1
12	Graham (2015)	151	4
13	Da Cruz (2016)	145	31

14	Albalate Del Sol (2013)	144	1
15	Pina (2009)	139	2
16	Hao (2021)	116	0
17	Ahn (2011)	113	3
18	Guillamon (2016)	108	2
19	Roever (2016)	104	0
20	Depaula (2018)	96	6

Source: Vosviewer.

For example, Da Cruz (2016) has received 145 citations and has a remarkable engagement power with 31 links.

Fig.4: Network, Overlay ve Density Visulation, (Occurrences) for Citation Analysis

Source: Vosviewer.

However, some studies may have a high number of citations but a low number of links, which may indicate that although these studies are recognized in the literature, they are less directly associated with other studies.

5. Conclusions

According to the bibliometric analysis of Web of Science indexed academic studies on transparency in local governments, it is understood that the first works were published in 1997 and there was a decrease in the number of publications after reaching the highest level in 2020.

The majority of this literature is in article format, and proceedings also have a significant share. While fields such as political science, management and economics are at the forefront, certain researchers (e.g. Ferry, Laurence; Tejedor-Romero, Francisca) stand out in academic productivity. Studies focus on SSCI and ESCI indexes, with Minho, Granada and London Universities coming to the fore. It is published in journals that focus on topics such as public policy and public services management, with English and Spanish being the most common languages. Broadcasts are made from more than 90 countries, especially Spain, America and England. Large publishing houses such as Taylor & Francis, Elsevier and Sage host the most publications. In the literature that attracts great attention from social sciences such as public administration and business economics, institutions such as the Spanish Government and the European Union are important funders. Research

focuses on sustainable development goals such as "quality education" and "reducing inequalities", with keywords such as "local government", "transparency" and "e-government" coming to the fore. It is seen that the keywords are collected in 9 different clusters. Less frequently used but important keywords include "sustainable development", "open data" and "participatory budgeting", which demonstrate the increasing importance of sustainability and open data use in local governments. Additionally, keywords such as "audit", "leadership" and "civil society" highlight the role of leadership and civil society in the process of ensuring transparency. These findings show that research on transparency in local governments covers a wide spectrum. For future research, it is recommended to examine concepts such as "smart cities", "social accountability" and "public information" in more depth and to increase comparative research on studies conducted in different countries and regions. In this way, knowledge on transparency in local governments can be increased by filling the gaps in the literature.

According to the citation analysis findings, the most cited study is Piotrowski (2007) with 351 citations and 64 links, while Kim (2009) is in second place with 209 citations and 4 links. Grimmelikhuijsen (2012) ranks third with 199 citations and 27 connections. Some studies may have a low number of links despite a high number of citations.

The scientific literature on transparency in local governments has shown an increasing momentum, especially until 2020, and the countries, institutions and research themes where academic production in this field is concentrated have been clearly revealed. In line with these findings, some concrete suggestions can be developed for politicians and local administrators. First of all, transparency practices need to be supported by digital tools. The prominence of concepts such as "e-government", "open data" and "participatory budgeting" in particular shows that it is critical for administrators to invest in these areas both to increase public trust and to ensure efficient use of resources. In addition, the institutionalization of "social accountability" and "public information" practices is important in terms of ensuring that transparency is not limited to providing information only, but also to allowing citizens to actively participate in decision-making processes. However, the prominence of concepts such as "leadership" and "civil society" necessitates that local governments become not only bureaucratic structures, but also structures that work in integration with society and establish trust-based relationships. In this context, it is a strategic step for administrators to increase their cooperation with civil society organizations and to spread transparency policies to a wider social base. Finally, developing policies compatible with smart city technologies and sustainable development goals will increase opportunities to benefit from both national and international funds and strengthen the long-term reliability and effectiveness of local governments.

Appendix

Table 14: Keyword List by Frequency

R an k	Keyword	Occur rences	Total Link Strength	R an k	Keyword	Occur rences	Total Link Strength
1	local government	236	396	38	efficiency	7	13
2	transparency	146	275	39	engagement	7	17
3	accountability	53	109	40	ghana	7	14
4	e-government	41	81	41	government transparency	7	4
5	local governments	35	52	42	political economy	7	15
6	social media	27	61	43	public information	7	14
7	municipalities	25	59	44	sustainable development	7	4
8	governance	24	35	45	twitter	7	10
9	corruption	22	33	46	new public management	6	10
10	decentralization	19	32	47	open data	6	13
11	open government	19	52	48	public policy	6	14
12	citizen participation	18	38	49	vietnam	6	12
13	participation	18	42	50	audit	5	16
14	sustainability	18	34	51	austerity	5	8
15	public sector	16	27	52	bangladesh	5	6
16	budget transparency	15	24	53	budgeting	5	14
17	china	15	12	54	citizens	5	11
18	good governance	15	30	55	civil society	5	6
19	public administration	14	29	56	communication	5	7
20	spain	14	46	57	e-democracy	5	11
21	trust	14	25	58	e-governance	5	12
22	democracy	11	28	59	evaluation	5	7
23	croatia	10	18	60	financial sustainability	5	8
24	decentralisation	10	8	61	government	5	8
25	websites	10	22	62	leadership	5	6

	corporate social responsibility	9	12	63	legitimacy	5	12
27	disclosure	9	22	64	municipality	5	10
28	facebook	9	15	65	nigeria	5	5
	fiscal transparency	9	5	66	open government data	5	7
30	indonesia	9	9	67	participatory budgeting	5	10
31	access to information	8	18	68	performance	5	9
32	e-participation	8	22	69	public management	5	10
33	england	8	18	70	smart cities	5	7
	gender	8	17	71	social accountabilit y	5	9
35	local governance	8	17	72	web 2.0	5	15
36	public participation	8	14	73	ict	5	8
37	tanzania	8	9	74	information disclosure	5	6
				75	internet	5	12

Source: Vosviewer.

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